

Effect of Carbetocin in Prevention of PPHGowri Sree Vukkem¹, Rita Ekka², Cherukuru Raja Nandini³¹Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Kamineni Institute of Medical Sciences, Narkatpally, Nalgonda, Telangana, India²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Kamineni Institute of Medical Sciences, Narkatpally, Nalgonda, Telangana, India³Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Kamineni Institute of Medical Sciences, Narkatpally, Nalgonda, Telangana, India

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Abstract:**Background:** Oxytocin is the main uterotonic drug for avoiding post-partum hemorrhage (PPH), which is a major cause of morbidity for mothers. Clinical studies have shown that carbetocin can reduce PPH risk without increasing the risk of major side effects. The purpose of current investigation was to evaluate carbetocin's potential for PPH prophylaxis.**Methods:** In this observational analysis, 100 women who had blood loss and major PPH incidents during vaginal (n=50) and cesarean (n=50) deliveries were included. Of these, half had carbetocin at tertiary care facility over the course of study period, which lasted for 2 years from January 2022 to December 2023. With SPSS version 25.0, the blood loss was approximated, and the findings were examined.**Results:** Between the groups having vaginal and cesarean deliveries, the mean age (~31 years), mean body mass index (~27kg/m²), and mean parity (~1.4) were comparable between those who received prophylactic carbetocin and those who did not. The intrapartum blood loss during vaginal birth was 227.28±157.32ml and 249.17±179.35ml, respectively; p=0.0873 for women treated with and without carbetocin. During CS, women who received carbetocin prophylaxis had significantly less mean± SD blood loss [651.47±321.58ml] than those who did not [831.38±361.96ml; p=0.0001]. Overall, total blood loss was considerably lower in women getting carbetocin prophylaxis than in those not (p<0.001).**Conclusion:** The preventive use of carbetocin significantly decreased blood loss during caesarean sections in cases of PPH when compared to vaginal deliveries.**Keywords:** Carbetocin, Cesarean, Mortality, Postpartum Hemorrhage, Vaginal Delivery.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Postpartum hemorrhage is the world's biggest cause of death for women, accounting for about one-fourth of all maternal deaths, despite tremendous efforts to reduce maternal mortality. [1,2] It also results in severe maternal morbidity, which can lead to long term impairment, emergency surgery, blood transfusions and hospitalization to an intensive care unit. Blood loss after a vaginal delivery of at least 500 ml and cesarean section of more than 1000ml is known as post-partum hemorrhage. [3] The most common cause of postpartum hemorrhage is uterine atony, or inadequate uterine contraction following childbirth. Over the past 15 years, postpartum hemorrhage has increased in both industrialized and developing nations. [4]

First line uterotonic medications increase uterine tone and promote contractions to reduce blood loss. [5,6] The use of additional uterotonic medicines is one of the necessary strategies for women who do not respond to first line therapy. [7] Actively man-

aged Third- stage labor (AMTSL) lowers the rate of severe PPH, the requirement for blood transfusions and the necessity for uterotonic therapy in the aftermath. [8]

Carbetocin, a synthetic analogue of oxytocin (100mg), can be given as IM and also, can be given as iv bolus over a minute in place of continuous oxytocin infusion to prevent PPH and reduce the need for therapeutic uterotonic medicines in elective cesarean surgery (level of evidence: 1B). Carbetocin functions more slowly than oxytocin because of its 40-minute of plasma half-life. [9] For the purpose of preventing Postpartum Haemorrhage (PPH) and uterine atony, Carbetocin administered intravenously caused rhythmic uterine contractions for around 60 minutes. As it also has significantly prolonged activity (~120 minutes; p¼0.02). [10-12] It is given in women who had epidural analgesia which increases the risk of PPH. Compared to oxytocin, carbetocin is better because it reduces the

risk of postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), greatly reduces the requirement for further uterotonic medicine, and improves uterine contractility during vaginal and cesarean sections. [13-15] Additionally, the adverse event profiles of oxytocin and carbetocin are comparable; yet, carbetocin is a superior option for cesarean deliveries because it is simpler to administer than conventional oxytocin regimens. [16] Given the importance of PPH management, the current study evaluated carbetocin's role in PPH prevention.

Material and Methods

During the course of two years, this observational study was carried out at a tertiary care hospital with women who had vaginal or cesarean delivery to compare the incidence of primary PPH. Before the trials began patients were requested to sign an informed consent form, and the institutional ethical committee granted ethical permission.

A total of 100 women who underwent vaginal (n=50) and c-sections (n=50) deliveries but administered carbetocin to prevent PPH were chosen using successive sampling. In both types of deliveries, half the women received carbetocin and other half did not. Based on inclusion and exclusion criteria, the patients underwent additional selection. Women with gestations ranging from 27 to 41 weeks participated in the study. Their age, height, weight, weeks of gestation, intrapartum phase,

postpartum period, and follow-up for four to six weeks after birth were recorded. Women with hypertension, heart disease, or preeclampsia were excluded.

After vaginal delivery or delivery by CS, a 100mg(1ml) bolus of carbetocin was given intravenously (iv) over the course of a minute after complete baby delivery eventhough Carbetocin can be given following placental delivery. Subsequently, during the two hours in the recovery room and every half hour during the postpartum observation period, the attending nurse kept an eye on the blood loss. Assessment of the blood loss was made possible by weighing the gauze and pad soakage. Blood loss of 500ml for vaginal births and 1000ml for cesarean deliveries was the hallmark of PPH. SSPS Statistics for windows, version 25.0, was used to do the statistical analysis. For both continuous and categorical variables, the student test and the chi square test are employed.

Results

The material features that were identified in the groups treated with and without prophylactic carbetocin for both vaginal and cesarean deliveries are shown in table1. The average age (about 31 years), average body mass index (about 27 kg/m²). And average parity (about 1.4) are some of these traits. There were as few special cases where mother parity and age varied.

Table 1: Characteristics of Study Patients

Variable	Vaginal delivery n=50		P value	Cesarean delivery n=50		P value
	With Carbetocin	Without Carbetocin		With Carbetocin	Without Carbetocin	
Maternal age(yr)	30.67±3.09	31.27±1.09	0.331	33.78±2.34	31.34±2.19	0.334
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.7±3.21	25.7±2.21	0.367	27.32±4.1	22.7±2.11	0.421
Parity	1.48±0.58	1.37±0.48	0.036	1.41±0.57	1.56±0.68	0.023

When giving birth vaginally, women treated with and without carbetocin experienced identical mean ±SD intrapartum blood loss (227.28±157.32ml & 249.17 ±179.35ml; p=0.0873). Between the groups receiving carbetocin and those without, there was no statistically significant difference in total blood loss (p=0.159). As anticipated, the mean ±SD blood loss following a cesarean section was nearly three to four times greater than of a vaginal deliv-

ery. However, compared to women not getting carbetocin prophylaxis (831.38±361.96 ml; p< 0.0001), those receiving it had a significantly lower mean ±SD blood loss during CS (651.47±321.58ML). Graph 1 indicates that overall, women who received carbetocin prophylaxis had significantly less total blood loss than those who did not (p,0.001).

The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends stringent management of third stage of labor to avoid post-partum hemorrhage. The preventive use of uterotonic medicines is the most important aspect of actively treating the third stage of labor, which has reduced the incidence of postpartum hemorrhage by nearly fifty percent. [17]

This observational study was carried out at a tertiary care institution and included 100 women with blood loss and an incidence of primary PPH during vaginal and cesarean deliveries (n=50 each). To avoid PPH, half of them had carbetocin treated. The outcomes aligned with the research on AMTSL in addition to carbetocin for cesarean sections as opposed to vaginal deliveries. When compared to other uterotonic drugs, prophylactic carbetocin did not significantly reduce intrapartum and early postpartum blood loss in the recovery room after vaginal deliveries. However, prophylactic carbetocin therapy greatly reduced blood loss during CS, as seen by the considerable decrease in total blood loss. [18,19] A recent study found that carbetocin, rather than oxytocin, is more effective in preventing PPH and treating it after vaginal births, especially high-risk deliveries. [15]

While blood loss is a useful indicator of efficacy, uterine tone and blood loss are also crucial indicators when further uterotonic medicine is needed. In a double blind, randomized, single center experiment carried out in United Kingdom, prophylactic oxytocin (5IU) was associated with higher necessity for additional oxytocic medications when used for cesarean deliveries than usage of prophylactic carbetocin. [19] Similar to this, in a small prospective controlled trial of cesarean births with at least one PPH risk factor, carbetocin demonstrated similar efficacy to oxytocin infusion in preserving uterine tone. It also has the bonus of lessening the sense of pain following surgery. [20] Regarding additional uterotonic needs, carbetocin was also found to be more effective than a continuous infusion of oxytocin in a prospective case control study

of cesarean deliveries. [18] It also showed a comparable hemodynamic profile and slight anti diuretic effect. A double-blind, randomized research on cesarean deliveries demonstrated the carbetocin was more reliable and effective than continuous oxytocin administration. This study also found that carbetocin maintained normal uterine tone and decreased excessive intraoperative blood loss during placental delivery. [21]

When compared to oxytocin, carbetocin significantly reduced the requirement for uterotonic medicine and the risk of PPH after cesarean deliveries alone, as per meta-analysis of 6 trials comparing the two drugs. Nevertheless, the need for uterine massage was found to decrease when carbetocin was administered after both vaginal and cesarean deliveries. Similarly, at 30 and 60 mins after delivery, the administration of carbetocin reduced the incidence of postpartum hypertension, the risk of unpleasant events including nausea and vomiting, and the mean blood loss. This was also discovered in the meta-analysis of 4 trials that contrasted intramuscular syntometrin and intramuscular carbetocin for vaginal birthing women. [13] We point out numerous possible limitations because the data is based on single location, even if the results of this observational study are consistent with body of knowledge on cesarean deliveries. Moreover, the absence of statistical significance in these deliveries may have been influenced by the ocular assessment of blood loss after vaginal delivery. We recognize that visual blood loss measurement is incredibly unreliable and has been shown to significantly underestimate the actual blood loss by upto 50% which makes it challenging to draw meaningfully comparable results from various studies. [22,23] Additional restrictions include the absence of segmentation based on maternal risk factors, age, vacuum or forceps delivery, and the requirement for CS, but the positive findings of this observational study demonstrate that carbetocin is useful in lowering blood loss and postpartum hem-

orrhage (PPH) after cesarean deliveries, which are both on the rise globally and continue to be a major risk factor for PPH. [24]

Conclusion

When prophylactic carbetocin was used, blood loss from vaginal deliveries during the intrapartum or early postpartum did not significantly decrease. However, it has been discovered that the proactive use of carbetocin after cesarean deliveries greatly lowers blood loss. When compared to vaginal deliveries, the incidence of PPH was dramatically reduced when carbetocin was used prophylactically. In actuality PPH associated with CS frequently has serious side effects and reassociates the use of an intricate uterine preservation techniques. Therefore, the finding that CS patient who received prophylactic carbetocin had a significant reduction in PPH may also suggest a lower risk of peripartum hysterectomy; however, our data does not support this later conclusion.

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